

Role of Social Media in Building an Employer Brand: A conceptual underpinning

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Abstract

Social media has become an important means of communication by organizations in the modern era. Identifying and recruiting talented employees is a major concern for business organizations today. Employer branding allows firms to create a positive image among current workers and potential employees in the job market for retaining and attracting the best talent. Social media platforms are increasingly being leveraged to disseminate the desired information among public to build a positive image of organization. Social media allows immediate user access and penetration to users in remote locations. This paper explores the literature to build a conceptual foundation of the role played by social media in building an employer brand.

Keywords: Social media; Employer branding; Recruitment strategy; Talent attraction; Talent engagement.

Introduction

Due to digitization and virtualization of work, the definition of success is no longer linked primarily to efficiency but to business agility. Digital technology has fundamentally revolutionized the way of doing business (Holland et al., 2022). Corporate social networks help the organizations build the perceived trust of employees, ensure greater transparency and promote collaborative work culture (Yang & Basile, 2022). Organizations today are witnessing a 'war for talent' due to their urge to hire the best employees. The talent shortage is compelling organizations to adopt employer branding strategy to appear as desirable places to work for employees. Employer branding thus acts as a powerful source of strategic competitive advantage for

organizations that not only helps to recruit the best candidates from the job market but also helps to engage and retain the talent present within the organization (Kucherov & Samokish, 2016). It can also be regarded as a long-term strategy for creating an authentic and appealing employer image for existing and future talent (Bondarouk et al., 2013). Building a strong employer brand produces positive attitudes in potential employees (Berthon et al., 2005), which enables businesses to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage in the labor market as they separate themselves from competitors (Aaker, 2003) and can potentially improve performance (Kashive & Khanna, 2017).

Organizations today have plenty of channels to communicate their employer brand, so it becomes imperative to determine which channels provide the best return on investment based on their recruitment goals (Gunesh & Maheshwari, 2019). Focusing on creating an employer brand online across channels such as the company website and social media pages is critical. Studies have highlighted upon important aspects of job seeker's awareness about employers, which fundamentally describes an employer brand like: the level of familiarity with the employer (Cable & Turban, 2001), employer reputation (Baum & Kabst, 2014), and the individual applicants' perceptions of accuracy in job and organizational characteristics (Aaker, 1996). Thus, the real benefits of social media would only be garnered by developing and communicating an effective employer branding strategy (Priyadarshini et al., 2017). Also, the information collected about applicants through social media is a valuable way of predicting the person-organization fit (Van Iddekinge et al., 2016). This paper thus explores the studies that have attempted to connect the use of social media to the employer branding strategy of the organization.

Social media in Organizations

Social media was defined by Marketo (2010) as "the production, consumption and exchange of information through online social interactions and platforms." It includes any internet technology that allows users to share their opinions and exchange information (Landers & Schmidt, 2016). The massive growth of social media, particularly in terms of users, holds significant consequences for transforming organizations, encouraging them to engage in several activities through social networks (Perdue, 2010). Social media, characterized by user-generated content, enables employees "to create, circulate, share, and exchange information in a variety of formats and with multiple communities" (Leonardi & Vaast, 2017, p. 150).

Social Networking Sites (SNS) are web-based applications based on Web 2.0 technology, which allow users to create content and communicate their identity and relationships directly (Boyd and Ellison, 2008). The growing popularity of social networking websites like LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter is forcing organizations to recognize the potential it provides in attracting today's young workforce.

Employer branding

In an economy where organizations compete to attract the best employees, the concept of employer branding has grown in importance (Ewing et al., 2002). The employer branding concept has emerged as an outcome of the application of marketing-like principles to human resource management practices. Ambler and Barrow (1996) defined employer brand as "the package of functional, economic and psychological benefits provided by employment, and identified with the employing company" (p. 187). It can also be defined as "a targeted,

long-term strategy to manage awareness and perceptions of employees, potential employees and related stakeholders with regards to a particular organization” (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004, p. 2). Berthon et al. (2005, p. 156) described it as “the envisioned benefits that a potential employee sees in working for a specific organization”. Effective employer branding creates “a distinct and desirable employer” image of the organization (Lievens et al., 2007, p. 48). Moroko and Uncles (2008) advocated that an employer brand can be considered a psychological contract between employer and employee. Thus, the employer brand propositions designed to ensure the rational and emotional benefits to current and future employees should be exhibited effectively (Pekkala & van Zoonen, 2022).

Employer branding and social media

Social networking is gaining attention as a popular recruitment tool in the modern era (Doherty, 2010). Social media and social networks offer vast opportunities for direct communication (for example, video, audio, posts, live chat, pictures, private messages) as well as provide excellent tools for communicating the brand meaning of the employer. Social Network Sites deliver several solutions to support employer branding through enhancing the organization’s value proposition, external marketing and internal marketing (Bondarouk et al., 2013).

By using social media, cognitive and affective processing of information about workplace choices can be enhanced, offering an invaluable opportunity to influence applicant interest, improve company visibility and target specific talent pools (Dutta, 2014). Those organizations that leverage social media efficiently have the opportunity to deepen links, and create trust, and loyalty with their target audiences (Powers et al., 2012).

With the rapid growth of social media in the talent market, job seekers are encouraged to consider the employer brands by visiting websites such as Glassdoor.com, Salary.com, Payscale.com, etc., when making decisions based on salaries and company ratings (Tanwar and Prasad, 2017). The increase in the number of users, the amount of information available, and the ease of access to social media have significantly changed the recruitment and hiring processes of organizations. As part of the hiring process, organizations today use social media (Peterson, 2014) to attract candidates and screen their profiles online (Ollington et al., 2013; Paik et al., 2014).

The psychology literature suggests that more the awareness regarding the organization and the job before joining, lower will be the turnover rate of employees (Wanous, 1973). The growing popularity of social networking websites such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter are pushing companies to recognize the potential social media presents to attract the young talent. The primary purpose of organizational communication before and during the recruitment process, is to attract potential job applicants to the organization (Breaugh & Starke, 2000). Job seekers interact with an organization psychologically through various information sources that shape their views and attitudes, and hence their overall image of the organization.

Hoffman and Fodor (2010) described the four Cs of connection, creation, consumption and control as the motivators behind social media engagement. With the current generation's increasing interaction on social media sites, companies are awakening to the opportunity to exploit these networks to create brand identities

and draw applicants to their organizations. Organizations that adopt these channels are deemed to be changing, creative and open to technological change.

Conclusion

This research has indicated that organizations must convey their employer brand on social media to attract job seekers. Although the empirical relation between social media marketing activities and employer branding is yet to be explored, the extant literature suggests that a correlation exists between social media marketing activities and the intention to apply. The question that arises out of this context for organizations would be to re-examine their processes and see whether they are prepared to take on this challenge of attracting and engaging young employees who value speed, openness, connectivity, and innovation.

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